

WORKING PAPER

*Submitted as a Citizens' Legislative Proposal under the Right to Petition the
Government (Article III, Section 4, 1987 Constitution)*

Proposed Title:

*An Act to Institutionalize Local Sandiganbayan Public Courts and
Enhance Anti-Corruption Mechanisms in the Philippines*

Submitted to:

The Republic of the Philippines,
through the Senate and the House of Representatives

Submitted by:

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I. TITLE OF THE PROPOSAL

“An Act to Institutionalize Local Sandiganbayan Public Courts and Enhance Anti-Corruption Mechanisms in the Philippines”

II. RATIONALE

The Philippines has a total of 2,068 high-ranking public officials, including the President, Vice President, 24 Senators, 1,493 Municipal Mayors, 149 City Mayors, 82 Governors, 254 District Representatives, and 64 party-list representatives. Excluding board members and city/municipal councilors for simplicity, a conservative estimate suggests that if hypothetically at least 90% of these officials were corrupt with incomplete, substandard, or ghost infrastructure projects, the time required to process legal actions sequentially would be 5,583 months, or 465 years.

To address systemic corruption efficiently, this proposal advocates for simultaneous and transparent public hearings at the local level, utilizing Sandiganbayan courts in every city, municipality, and province. This would reduce processing time to approximately 3 to 6 months, ensuring swift accountability.

This proposal is written *for Filipino children who are deprived of education and a better future because of corruption and greed*, emphasizing the urgent need for systemic reform.

This working paper emphasizes:

- The need to empower constitutional bodies such as the Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan with independence and automatic budget allocation.
- Hiring sufficient lawyers and accountants proportional to the estimated number of corrupt officials.
- Conducting all hearings publicly, with local constituents invited and proceedings streamed online for transparency.
- Using open venues such as gymnasiums and evacuation centers to ensure access and participation.

Systemic corruption in the Philippines requires a systemic solution.

This proposal aims to institutionalize a structured, transparent, and local-level approach to accountability through the establishment of Local Sandiganbayan Public Courts.

III. IMPORTANT PROVISIONS

1. **Local Sandiganbayan Courts:** Establish Sandiganbayan public courts in every city, municipality, and province.
2. **Public Hearings:** Mandate all hearings to be fully transparent and open to constituents, with live streaming on platforms such as Facebook and YouTube.
3. **Resource Allocation:** Automatically allocate sufficient budget to the Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan to support operations and staffing.
4. **Hiring of Staff:** Employ adequate numbers of lawyers, accountants, and support staff proportionate to the volume of cases expected.
5. **Venue Requirements:** Allow hearings in public spaces, including gyms, open halls, and evacuation centers, to accommodate large audiences.
6. **Expedited Case Resolution:** Implement simultaneous case processing to ensure final decisions within *3 to 6 months* for high-ranking public officials.

IV. REQUEST FOR CONSIDERATION

I respectfully submit this **Working Paper** for consideration. Its implementation aims to drastically reduce the time required to hold corrupt officials accountable, strengthen anti-corruption institutions, and restore public trust in governance.

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Note: *This document presents a core idea and does not yet constitute a fully drafted proposed law with detailed sections. It is intended as a foundation for further development and refinement in future legislative work.*

*The majority of the first 100 Proposed Laws are included in *The Great Nation 2025* started on December 9, 2024. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5310407> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5310407>.*

Additional proposed laws will be gradually published in the future.

Annex A - Original Facebook Post

The following is the unedited original Facebook post by the author, published on October 5, 2025, which serves as supporting context for this working paper:

Proposed Law #105: Systematic and Transparent Localized Sandiganbayan Public Hearings Involving Corrupt Public Officials in every City, Municipality and Province

There's one President and one Vice President in the Philippines.

There are 24 Senators, 1,493 Municipal Mayors, 149 City Mayors, 82 Governors, 254 District Representatives, and 64 Party-list Representatives.

In total, there are 2,068 number of high-ranking politicians in the Philippines. I exclude the board members, and city/municipal councilors for simplicity of the computation.

If, hypothetically, at least 90% of them are corrupt and have incomplete/substandard/ghost infrastructure projects, and on average it will take three months to have a final Sandiganbayan court decision, then it would take x number of months or years to put all of the corrupt politicians in jail.

$2,068 \times 90\% = 1,861$

x number of months if the cases will be process on SEQUENCE or one case at a time. One case every three months.

5,583 months or 465 years

While,

x number of months if the cases will be process SIMULTANEOUSLY using systematic and transparent Sandiganbayan Public Hearing in every city, municipality and province.

$1,493 + 149 + 82 = 1,724$ local Sandiganbayan courts

3 to 6 months only since there are 1,861 high ranking public officials.

The above excludes the DPWH/LGU Engineer and the Contractor of the infrastructure project. It will take many many months before the Philippines can put all corrupt public officials in jail if done in SEQUENCE compared to SIMULTANEOUS (three to six months) if there is a local Sandiganbayan Court in every City, Municipality and Province.

Also, the computation is just a conservative estimate. The three months final court decision is too ideal in the Philippines, unless otherwise institutionalised.

The corruption in the Philippines is systemic and unprecedented in world history. We need a systemic solution.

Empower the existing constitutional bodies such as the Commission on Audit (COA), Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan. Make them highly independent, with the budget automatically allocated to them.

Hire as many lawyers and accountants as possible, in proportion to the estimated number of corrupt public officials.

Then make all hearings public, like the exact transparency in the Blue Ribbon Committee with Facebook and YouTube Live.

All local constituents are invited to every local Sandiganbayan public hearing, so the venue could be open spaces such as gymnasiums and evacuation centers.